

**Simulation of SCADA Message Structure Using the
Tele-control Protocol IEC 60870-5-101**

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إهداء

إلى أمي الغالية

إلى روح أبي الغالي الذي كان حريصا على أن أكمل هذا العمل

إلى زوجتي العزيزة.....

إلى إخوتي.....

إلى كل أفراد العائلة

إلى عبدالمجيد.....

إلى الرائع دوما د.خالد

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ABSTRACT

The SCADA systems are very important to control widely distributed power networks. Each SCADA system uses a tele-control protocol for communication between stations, one of the commonly used protocols is the IEC60870-5-101 standard tele-control protocol .

For this study, the IEC60870-5-101 was selected to simulate SCADA signals transferring between two stations due to its wide spread use in the tele-control systems, and it is also considered as a base structure for modern tele-control systems such as IEC60870-5-104.

The aim of this simulation is to study the behavior of the tele-control protocol. Visual basic programming language was used to implement this simulation. The simulation was done by taking a transformer tap changer as an example for the experiment. For this tap changer, Regulating commands from the central station (control centre) were sent to the controlled station(remote station) in order to raise or lower the tap changer position then the step position indications were sent from the controlled station to the central station.

Additional SCADA functions, such as generation of alarms and implementation of interlocks, which are not present in the existing SCADA systems, were added within centre station besides its generation in the remote station.

المستخلص

يعتبر استخدام أنظمة التحكم المشرف من الأهمية بمكان في التحكم بأنظمة القدرة .كل نظام من أنظمة التحكم المشرف يستخدم احد بروتوكولات الاتصال التحكمي للاتصال بين مركزالتحكم في الشبكة والمحطات. احد اهم هذه البروتوكولات هو البروتوكول IEC60870-5-101.

في هذه الدراسة تم اختيار هذا البروتوكول لمحاكاة نقل اشارات التحكم المشرف بين المحطات نسبة لانتشاره الواسع و لكونه قاعدة لبروتوكولات الاتصال التحكمي الحديثة مثل IEC60870-5-104 .

الغرض من هذه المحاكاة هو دراسة التغيرات التي يحدثها البروتوكول التحكمي في الإشارات المرسله. تم استخدام لغة البرمجة Visual Basic لعمل المحاكاة.

تم عمل المحاكاة باخذ مغير عدد لفائف الجانب الاولي من محول قدرة كمثال لهذه التجربة.تم ارسال اوامر تشغيل لتغيير عدد اللفايف (زيادة او نقصان) من مركز التحكم وتم استلام الاوامر وتنفيذها في المحطة الفرعية بغرض تحسين الجهد.ومن ثم تم ارسال اشارات الموضع الخاصة بمغيرعدد اللفايف من المحطة الي مركز التحكم.

كما تمت إضافة بعض الإشارات الجديدة من مركز التحكم كالانذارات وقيود التشغيل والتي يتم توليدها عادة بالمحطات الطرفية ومن ثم ارسالها لمركز التحكم, في هذه المحاكاة تم توليد هذه الاشارات من مركز التحكم بالإضافة لتولييدها من المحطة.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

The increasing complexity of electrical networks, and its very high interconnection grade, causes a need of an over all control system that manages the whole network including the monitoring of the system states and making necessary control instructions to guarantee the stability of the power system. However, such complex system will consist of a number of stations distributed in different areas, and in order to keep in continuous monitoring of them, it is not easy to keep operators (shifts) in each station and to use the telephone lines to contact with the shift staff to get the information and to order for certain commands. This will increase the number of the facility employees and also will increase the response time during failures.

To solve these problems the SCADA system is used. Many companies and institutes developed various versions of SCADA system that enables to monitor and instruct equipments inside stations in remote areas from a unique centre called the control centre.

1.2 Project objective

The objective of this project is to study the main features and functions of the SCADA system that is used in power networks and communication protocols used to link between the different facilities in the same system. This study simulates an easy system that operates with a standard tele-control protocol IEC 60870-5-101.

1.3 Approaches

For implementation, the simulation was made using Visual Basic programming language version 6.0, which runs under windows. Visual basic was selected because it combines high level programming languages that allow the user to easily develop useful Microsoft Windows applications with ability to create graphical programs with little coding and the medium level languages in case the programmer wants to interface with intelligent devices. The simulation program follows the simulated signals from source to destination including the changes done by communication protocols.

1.4 Thesis layout

This thesis was structured in several parts, each part discuss and demonstrate many details associate with SCADA system.

Firstly, Chapter one states the problem and the project purpose which answered many questions such as why using the SCADA system

In Chapter two, an introduction to the SCADA system gives more details and theory and also a detail description of the tele-control protocols is given including protocol layers and the frame structure.

In the third chapter, a software simulation depending on the message structure of a tele-control protocol was developed using the Visual Basic programming language.

Chapter four shows the program interface menus and the produced results.

Lastly in Chapter five details conclusion was made to determine the main advantages of these experimental efforts. And recommendations were made to make useful utilization of this software in the real application.

Chapter 2

SCADA System

&

IEC 60 870-5-101 Tele- control Protocol

2.1 What's SCADA?

SCADA is the technology that enables a centre of operations to collect data from one or more distant facilities and send control instructions to these facilities. It makes it unnecessary for an operator to be assigned to stay at or frequently visits remote locations when those locations operate normally.

2.2 Definition of SCADA

SCADA is an acronym that's formed from the first letters of the term (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition).

A SCADA system allows an operator to make set point changes on distance process controllers, to open or close valves or switches, to monitor alarms, to gather measurement information from a location and control to a widely distributed process such as an oil or gas field, pipe line system or hydroelectric generating complex. When the dimensions of the process become very large, hundred or even thousands of kilometers from one and to the others we can appreciate the benefits SCADA offers in terms of reducing the cost of routine visits to monitor facilities operation. These benefits will grow ever more if the facilities are very remote and require extreme effort (e.g. a helicopter trip) to visit.

2.3 SCADA Applications

SCADA technology is best applied to process that is:-

- Spread over large area.
- Relativity simple to control and monitor.
- Require frequent, regular, or immediate intervention.

The following examples of such process show the range of application types SCADA is suitable for:

- Electric transmission systems may cover thousands of kilometers, can be controlled by opening and closing switches, and must respond almost immediately to load changes on the lines.
- Groups of small hydroelectric generating stations that are turned on and off in response to customer demand. They can be controlled by opening and closing valve to the turbine, they must be monitored continuously, and they need respond relatively quickly to demands on the electrical power grid.
- Oil or gas production facilities including well, gathering systems, fluid measurement equipments and pumps. They require some controls such as turning motors on and off. Also there is a need to gather meter information regularly and must respond quickly to conditions in the rest of the field.
- Pipelines for gas, oil, chemicals or water have elements that are located at varying distances from a central room point, can be controlled by opening and closing valves of starting and stopping pumps, and must be capable of responding quickly to market conditions.
- Irrigation systems can be controlled by opening and closings valves, and require the gathering of meter values for the water supplies to consumers.

Typical signal gathered from remote locations include alarms, status indications, analogue values, and totalized meter values. Similarly, signal sent from SCADA's central location to the remote site are usually limited to discrete binary bit changes or to analogue values addressed to a device at the process. An

example of a binary bit change could be an instruction ordering a motor to stop. An example of analogue value could be an instruction to change a value controller set point to 75 percent.

2.4 SCADA elements

Figure 2-1 shows the major components of a SCADA system. At center is the operator, who access the system by means of an operator interface device or operator console, the operator console functions as the operator window to the process it consist of a video display unit that displays the real time data about the process and a key board for inputting the operators commands or message back to the process. Other cursor positioning devices, such as a rack ball, mouse or touch screen may be used. If the system is very simple, it may be sufficient to have a set of annunciate windows that mimic the condition of the remote process.

Figure 2-1 Major components of a SCADA system

The operator interfaces with the master terminal unit (MTU), which is the system controller, some industries use the name (host computer) instead of (MTU). The (MTU) in modern SCADA systems is always based on a computer.

It may be scheduled to request an update from each remote terminal unit (RTU) every certain time.

MTUs must communicate with RTUs that are located away from the central location. A SCADA system may have a few as one RTU or as many as several hundreds.

There are two common media of communication:-

- Land line, which takes the form of optical fiber cable or electrical cables and this type may either be owned by the company or leased from the telephone utility.
- Radio.

Some electrical utilities use the optical fiber in ground wire (OPGW) within the transmission lines as communication media.

Normally the MTU will have auxiliary devices e.g. printers and memory arrays attached to it, these devices are considered to be a part of it.

The RTU communicates with MTU by a modulated signal on cable or radio. Each RTU must have the capability to understand that a message directed to it, to decode the message, to act on the message, to respond if necessary and to shut down to wait a new message. Acting on a message may be a very complex procedure, it may require:-

- Checking the present position of the field equipment.
- Comparing the existing position to the required position.
- Checking the interlocks.
- Sending the signal to the field device to change the state.

- Checking a set of switches to ensure that the message order was obeyed.
- Sending message back to the MTU to confirm that the new condition has been done. Because of this complexity most RTUs are based on computer technology.

2.4.1 Remote terminal unit

The remote terminal unit (RTU) gathers information from the field about:-

- Analogue values.
- Alarms and status points.
- Metered amounts.

Also it sends commands to field devices.

The RTU has the ability to receive and send measures to field devices in serial format.

Figure 2.2 Signals coming to the RTU

Figure 2.3 Signals from the RTU

2.4.1.1 Communication Interface

RTUs are essentially micro computers with special equipment at one end and designed to interface with the communication link and with special equipments at the other end to interface with the field equipments. While the

RTU is in receiving mode the communication interface receives a serial signal from the communication medium. This signal is conditioned to a stream of bits that are either ones or zeros. In this stage the signal is not analogue, although some analogue signals may have been coded into binary for transmission to the RTU. Using rules that were established when the communication protocol was developed. Another part of the communication interface interprets the strings of ones and zeros and passes the information on to the rest of the RTU. If the first bit of message is not recognized the message is often not understood. It must be always in listening mode (except when it is transmitting). All these functions are accomplished with the central processing units (CPU).

2.4.1.2 RTU functions

2.4.1.2.1 Discrete control

This type is used when we need to send a command that requires only one bit to be done for example opening valves requires sending bit (1) in the desired address.

2.4.1.2.2 Analogue control

In this type set points are sent, so more than one bit is sent to complete the set point value , for example if we want to open a valve to 75% of its opening the following pattern will be sent.

Bit0	Bit1	Bit2	Bit3	Bit4	Bit5	Bit6	Bit7
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
50%	25%	12.5%	6.25%	3.125%	1.56%	0.75%	0.39%

Figure: 2.4 Bit pattern for analogue set point.

2.4.1.2.3 Pulse control

This type is seldom used and it allows a stepper to be incremented or decremented by a specific number of steps.

2.4.1.2.4 Monitor discrete signals

This type is used to monitor alarms and status points when a bit 1 is present that means the alarms are present or the status is on.

2.4.1.2.5 Monitor analogue signals

It is important to monitor a process parameter to get more than a binary amount of information, for example:

- The actual height of a liquid in a tank
- The speed of a motor
- The level of radiation
- The voltage, current, power, energy and power factor in power stations.

In these situations a sensor is provided that changes the parameter of interest to a more easily monitored quantity, such as current.

2.4.2 Master terminal unit (MTU)

It is the device located in the centre of each SCADA system that issues all the commands, gather all the information, passes other information on to associated systems and interfaces with the operators.

To do all these jobs a very detailed description of the field signals that are connected to the system must be available to the MTUs processor. To be handled in the most time-effective manner, this description must be arranged in hierarchical form.

2.4.2.1 MTU Operators Windows

The operators at the SCADA system centre shall have the following windows:-

- A window that contains the layout of the original system (for electrical networks will include the transmission lines, switches, transformers, generators ...etc). This window will display the status indication, the metered values and the analogue measurements.
- Alarm window list shows the alarms with its time.
- Event list shows all the events that happened with time.
- Engineering window for the modifications to be made by the SCADA system engineer.

2.4.2.2 Communication Interface

The MTU must send information to each RTU. It uses the medium that the RTU uses to send information to it. It also uses the same protocol as the RTU. The MTU is responsible for initiating conversations with each RTU.

2.5 Communication Protocols

Communication Protocols are the grammars through which computer-based devices communicate with one another the way they organize, and transmit the bits and bytes of electronic on-off (binary) signals whose patterns encode data. Simply, a protocol is a set of rules that governs how message containing data

and control information are assembled at a source for their transmission across the network and then disassembled when they reach their destination.

2.5.1 Standardizations of Protocols

Without standards it is almost impossible for utilities to choose several suppliers within one IT infrastructure. When using a proprietary protocol, a lot of custom-made, time-consuming and expensive solutions – gateways or interface modules - are usually necessary to build up a multi-vendor communication environment. Therefore, the major reasons for setting up protocol communication standards are:

- Optimization of cost per unit.
- Risk management
- Flexibility.

2.5.2 Anatomy of a communication Protocol

Most standards organizations use a layered model or stack to develop protocol specifications, with each layer performing some very specific functions and services.

2.5.3 The open Systems Interconnect Reference Model

The Open Systems Interconnect (OSI) reference model is a layered set of protocols to facilitate open communications between computer networks. It was developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) in conjunction with the Consultative Committee on International Telegraphy and Telephony (CCITT).

The purpose of the OSI communication model is to make multi vendor networking easy to implement, thereby reducing the overall costs and enhancing the level of system integration that normally could be realized with constantly changing and expanding protocol solutions.

2.5.4 The 7 - Layer Stack

The 7-Layer stack is based on established international ISO protocol standards. The architecture intended to provide full communications functionality based on the OSI Reference Model and is capable of supporting the majority and the industry data communication requirements.

The top three layers are directly concerned with the actual application messages being sent between stations. The bottom four layers are concerned with the method used to transport those messages between stations.

Figure 2.5 7-Layers Protocol Structure

2.5.5 The 3 - Layer Stack

The 3-layer stack is also based on stable international standards. The 3-layer stack provides a simpler mechanism for data communication.

Figure 2.6 3-Layers Protocol Structure

2.5.6 Tele-control Protocol

The large growth of power networks, pipelines and water supply system and the very high interconnection grade, causes a growing need of communication between the different stations controlled by the SCADA system. However, such equipments are commonly of different period, technology and vender. In this situation, the communication between them becomes a serious problem. Many efforts have been accomplished to define a set of standardized protocols, for both the centre-remote communication and for the link between centers of the same levels.

The standard permits the user of the tele-control to specify/choose his system strategy for using the protocol provisions in ways that solve his system problems.

2.6 The IEC Protocol Series

The IEC Technical Committee 57 (TC57) have developed a protocol standard for tele-control, tele-protection, and associated telecommunications for electric power systems. The result of this work is IEC 870-5 series, which is one of the standard tele-control protocols that used in the 90s and still being updated regularly according to new technologies and industry requirements. There are many version of the IEC 60870-5 standard. The serial versions tele-control scheme TCS101 and tele-protection scheme PCS103 are mostly used all over the world, while the tele-control scheme TCS104, which was published by the end of 2000, is based on TCS101 and uses broadband (TCP/IP) technology. A lot of utilities have started already or will start to migrate from proprietary protocols to the serial TCS101/PCS103 or the TCS104. An example of the tele-control standards (IEC 870 - 5) is shown in figure (2.7) [3], [5].

Figure 2.7 An example of the tele-control standards (IEC 870 - 5)

2.7 IEC 60870 – 5 – 101 Protocol

This is the most commonly tele-control protocol used all over the world. The model used in this protocol has fewer layers, because some of the facilities supported by the full seven layer model are not required and enhanced working

of the remaining facilities is desired hence the model is often called the enhanced performance architecture (EPA) Model. [3], [5]

Two stations, shown in Figure (2.8), are communicating together by using the EPA model. Each station has a “stack” of protocol layers providing communication services to the station application processes at top and accessing the communications medium at the bottom.

Figure 2.8 Two stations communicating using EPA Model

Application data is accepted at the top of the protocol stack in one station and passes down through the stack, acquiring in each layer any necessary extra data needed to control the working of the protocol until it emerges in serial form at the bottom. It is then transmitted to the other station where it enters at the

bottom of protocol stack. The data passes up this stack having the control data stripped off layer by layer until the original application data emerges at the top and is passed to the application processes in destination station.

This is called “peer to peer “communication because all data originating in a particular layer is transported to the same layer in the remote station.

2.7.1 Network configurations

The following fixed network configurations are supported:

- Point - to - point
- Multiple points - to - point
- Party line
- Redundant line

Figure 2.9 Network configuration

2.7.2 Message structure

Serial messages have a nested structure, which derives from the layered structure of the protocol. The ASDU (Application service Data unit) is a block of data being sent from the application processes in another station. ASDU is specified as frames with variable length.

Frame with variable length used in IEC 870-5-101 starts with:-[1], [4], [6]

- One byte Start Character.
- Two bytes Frame Length.
- One byte Start Character.
- One byte Control Field.

And stops with:-

- One byte Checksum.
- One byte Stop Character.

The ASDU is composed of a Data Unit Identifier and one or more Information Objects. The Data Unit Identifier has always the same structure for all ASDUs.

The Information Objects of an ASDU are always of the same structure and type, which are defined in the type identification field.

The structure of the data unit identifier is:

- One byte Type Identification.
- One byte Variable Structure Qualifier.
- One/two bytes Cause of Transmission.
- One /two bytes Common Address of ASDU.

The structure of the information object is:

- Information objects identifier.
- Set of information elements.
- Time tag of information object (optional).

2.7.2.1 Start / stop character

Start and stop characters have always the same structure for all ASDU messages. Each character has a fixed defined bit pattern, which holds one byte as shown in Figure (2.10).[1],[6]

Figure 2.10 Start /Stop character format.

2.7.2.2 Length character

Length character specifies the number and subsequent user data bytes including the control and address fields. It has a range up to 255 bytes, which must be a parameter in the controlled station –see Figure (2.11) the two bytes contain the same value of the length number. [1], [6]

Bit	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
	2^7	2^6	2^5	2^4	2^3	2^2	2^1	2^0
	2^7	2^6	2^5	2^4	2^3	2^2	2^1	2^0

Figure 2.11: Length character field

2.7.2.3 Control field

The control field contains information that characterizes the direction of the message, the type of the service provided and supports control functions for suppressing losses or duplications of messages.[1],[6]

Figure 2.12 Control field for unbalanced mode

2.7.2.4 Type identification

Type Identification Byte1 defines structure, type and format of the following Information object (s).

Type identification is defined as:

TYPE IDENTIFICATION: = UI8 [1...8] <1...255>

Figure 2.13 Type Identification Structure

Information objects with or without time tags are distinguished with different numbers of the type Identification. [1], [6]

ASDUs with undefined values of type Identification are acknowledged negatively and discarded by both controlling and controlled stations.

Definition of the semantics of the values of the type identification field:

The value <0> is not used. The range of values (numbers) 1 to 127 is defined. The range of numbers 128 to 255 is not defined. Full interoperability would be obtained only when using ASDUs having type Identification numbers in the range 1 to 127.

In The following, shown the definition of type identification numbers for process and system information in monitor and control direction.

Type identification: = UI8 [1...8] <1...255>

- <1...127>:= for standard definitions from IEC 870-5-101 standard
- <128...135>:= reserved for routing of messages (private range)
- <136...255>:= for special use (private range)

2.7.2.5 Variable structure qualifier

Byte 2 of the data unit identifier of the ASDU defines the variable structure qualifier which is specified in the following.

Definition of the semantics of the values of the Variable Structure Qualifier field: [1], [6]

Variable structure qualifier: = CP8 {number, SQ}

Number=N: = UI7 [1...7] <0...127>

- <0>:= ASDU contains no information object
- <1..127> := number of information object or elements

SQ=Single/sequence: = BS1 [8] <0...1>.

- <0>:= addressing of an individual element or combination of elements in a number of information object of the same type.
- <1>:= addressing of a sequence of information elements in one object.
- SQ<0>and N<0...127>:= number of information object.
- SQ<1>and N<0...127>:= number of information elements of a single object per ASDU

The SQ bit specifies the method of addressing the following information objects or elements.

SQ = 0: Each single element or a combination of elements is addressed by the information object address. The ASDU may consist of one or more than one equal information objects. The number N is binary coded and defines the number of the information objects.

SQ = 1: A sequence of equal information objects (e.g. measured values of identical format) is addressed by the information object address.

The information object address specifies the associated address of the first information element of the sequence.

The following information elements are identified by numbers incrementing continuously by +1 from this offset. The number N is binary coded and defines the number of the information element. In case of a sequence of information elements only one information object ASDU is allocated.

2.7.2.6 Cause of transmission

Byte 3 of the data unit identifier of the ASDU defines the cause of transmission field which is specified in the following. [1], [6]

Figure 2.14 Cause of transmission field

Definition of the semantics of the values of the cause of transmission field:

Cause of transmission: = CP16 {Cause, P/N, T, Originator Address (opt)}

Cause := UI6 [1...6] <0...63>

- <0> := not defined
- <1...63> := number of cause

- <1...47> := for standard definitions of this companion standard (compatible range),

- <48...63> := for special use (private range)

P/N := BS1 [7] <0...1>

- <0> := positive confirm
- <1> := negative confirm

T=test := BS1 [8] <0...1>

- <0> := no test
- <1> := test

The cause of transmission directs the ASDU to a specific application task (program) for processing.

The P/N-bit indicates the positive or negative confirmation of activation requested by the primary application function. In the case of irrelevance the P/N-bit is zero.

In addition to the cause the test-bit defines ASDUs which were generated during test conditions. It is used e.g. to test transmission and equipment without controlling the process.

ASDUs marked (CON) in control direction are confirmed application services and may be mirrored in monitor direction with different cause of transmission.

If the originator address is not used and there is more than a single source in a system defined, the ASDUs in monitor direction have to be directed to all relevant sources of the system. In this case the specific affected source has to select its specific ASDUs.

2.7.2.7 Common Address of ASDUs

The common address of the ASDU defines the station address and has a length, which is fixed per system (one or two bytes). Function codes of the common address for both one and two byte's modes are described in table (2.1).

Function	Common Address One octet Range <0 – 255>	Common Address Two octets Range <0 – 65535>
Not used	Common Address = 0	Common Address = 0
Station address	Common Address = <1..254>	Common Address = <1..65534>
Global address	Common Address = <255>	Common Address = <65535>

Table 2.1 Function Code of the common Address

2.7.2.8 Information Object

The information object consists of information object identifier, set of information elements and time tag of object. The information object identifier consists only of (one, two or three bytes) of information object address, which used as destination address in control direction and as source address in monitor direction. The zero number in all types (one, two and three bytes), reflects that the information object address is irrelevant

The second field of information object is a set of information elements, which represents the transmitted data. There are different types of data depend on the required application and protocol used.

For example command signals (tests and reset process), measured values (current, voltage, power, and frequency) and communication signals (initiation and end of initiation).

2.7.2.8.1 Information objects in monitor direction:

- <1>:= Single-point information
- <3>:= Double Point information
- <5>:= Step position information
- <7>:= Bit string of 32 bit
- <8>:= Bit string of 32 bit with time tag
- <9>:= Measured value, normalized value
- <10>:= Measured value, normalized value with time tag
- <11>:= Measured value, scaled value
- <12>:= Measured value, scaled value with time tag
- <13>:= Measured value, short floating point value
- <15>:= Integrated totals
- <16>:= Integrated totals with time tag
- <17>:= Event of protection equipment with time tag
- <18>:= Packed start events of protection equipment with time tag
- <19>:= Packed output circuit information of protection equipment with time tag

- <20>:= Packed single point information with time tag
- <21>:= Measured value, normalized value without quality descriptor
- <30>:= Single-point information with time tag
- <31>:= Double-point information with time tag
- <32>:= Step position information with time tag
- <33>:= Bit string of 32 bit with time tag
- <36>:= Measured value, short floating point value with time tag

2.7.2.8.2 Information objects in control direction:

- <45>:= Single command
- <46>:= Double command
- <47>:= Regulating step command
- <48>:= Set point command, normalized value
- <51>:= Bit string of 32 bit

Chapter 3

Simulation Program

3.1 Simulation Description

The program simulates transferring of data between a secondary station and a primary station using the concepts of the standard IEC60 870-5-101 tele-control protocol. The primary station represents a load dispatch centre (Control Centre), which monitors and controls power flow into several remote stations. The secondary station represents one of the remote stations. The remote station contains several line feeders, power transformers, bus bars, control devices and protection equipments.

The primary station sends controlling commands (open, close, step up, step down, reset) to the secondary station, while the later sends status signals (indications, alarms, measurements) to the primary station for monitoring.

Only one Transformer tap changer was selected by the program to apply the use of tele-control protocol.

The tap changer step position indication and the transformer secondary side voltage were selected to be the information objects of the application service data unit (ASDU) in the direction from remote station to the control centre while the tap changer regulating commands (Raise & Lower) were selected to be the application service data unit (ASDU) in the direction from control centre to the remote station.

3.2 Program procedures

The following section represents the main procedures that were used in the simulation.

3.2.1 Start Simulation procedure

This procedure represents the initiation procedure in addition to the application service data unit (ASDU) generation, sending and receiving procedures.

The initiation was made by using the following procedures:-[1], [6]

- Centre Request.
- Station Receive.
- Station Respond

The “Generate Reading” procedure generates the information elements for the tap changer. Values of voltage and step position were set to certain starting values.

“Station send ASDU”, “Centre receive ASDU”, “Centre send ASDU” and “Station receive ASDU” procedures perform sending and receiving the frame of variable length containing ASDU.

The flowchart of the “Start Simulation_click” procedure is shown in Figure (3.1).

Figure (3.1): Flow chart of Start Simulation click procedure.

3.2.2 Centre Request procedure

In this procedure the primary station generates a frame of fixed length, which represents a message known as request status of the link. Start, control field, checksum and stop characters were generated to construct the frame. [1], [6]. The control field character of this message takes binary byte (0.1.0.0.1.0.0.1), which was represented by decimal number “73”. The flowchart of this procedure is shown in Figure (3.2).

Figure (3.2) Flow chart of Primary Request procedure

3.2.3 Secondary Receive request procedure

The secondary station checks the received frame in the input/output buffer and replies with relative message. For simplification, the request status of the link message (with control field of decimal "73") is replied by the respond status of the link message (with control field of decimal "11").

The reset of the remote link message (with control field of decimal "64") is replied by the acknowledge message (with control field of decimal "0"). [1], [6]

Figures (3.3) show flow chart of Secondary Receive procedure.

Figures (3.3) Flow chart of Secondary Receive procedure

3.2.4 Secondary sends ASDU procedure

After receiving the request message from the master station, the secondary station generates a variable length frame. This frame is built from start and stop characters in addition to the application service data unit (ASDU) of the step position indication of the tap changer.

The table 3.1 shows the frame characters values when sending from secondary.

Field Name	Value	Remark
Start field	68	Frames with variable length start with 68
Frame length	6	
Frame length	6	
Start field	68	
Control field	8	
Type identification	5	Step Position Indication
No of information elements	1	
Cause of transmission	2	In case of background scan
	11	In case of change due to remote control
Common address	10	
Information object address	30	
Information element	1...21	
Check sum	57..67	Equal sum of user defined data
Stop field	68	Frames with variable length stop with 68

Table 3.1 Frame structure of message from remote station

Flowchart for the procedure is shown in Figure (3.4).

Figure (3.4): Flow chart of Secondary Send ASDU procedure.

3.2.5 Centre sends ASDU procedure

In this procedure depending on the action taken by the user of simulator (the operator) the centre generates a variable length frame with the following frame fields so as to command the remote station with the action needed:

Field Name	Value	Remark
Start field	68	Frames with variable length start with 68
Frame length	6	
Frame length	6	
Start field	68	
Control field	65	
Type identification	47	Regulating step command
No of information elements	1	
Cause of transmission	6	"Activation"
Common address	10	
Information object address	40	
Information element	2	Raise Command
	1	Lower Command
Check sum	100	Equal sum of user defined data
Stop field	68	Frames with variable length stop with 68

Table 3.2 Frame structure of message from centre

The following flow chart shows the centre send procedure:

Figure 3.5 Flow chart shows the centre send procedure

3.2.6 Secondary receive ASDU procedure

In this Procedure the secondary checks the received frame with variable length from centre and responds depending on the information element value, if the information element value is "1" the station decrements the tap changer step position by "1" and if the value is "2" the tap changer position is incremented by "1".

Figure 3.6 (a) Flow chart shows the secondary receive procedure

Figure 3.6 (b) Flow chart shows the secondary receive procedure

3.2.7 Centre receive ASDU procedure

In this procedure the centre checks the received variable length frame fields and depending on the value of the information element field it changes the corresponding measurement field in the SCADA system interface to match the new value in the station.

A flow chart describing this procedure is drawn in figure (3.7)

Figure 3.7 Flow chart shows the secondary receive procedure

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Program Interface

In the first run of the simulation program a Main Window appears as shown in figure (4.1); this window is divided into two sections. The first section in the left hand side represents the remote station while the right hand section represents the control centre.

The Main Window consists of the following objects:

A: File menu which consist of two sub menus:

- Start Simulation
- Quit

B: Message Structure Menu which consist of four sub menus:

- Frames from Centre.
- Frames from Remote Station.
- Centre request frame.
- Station respond frame.

C: Three text boxes that shows:

- Tap changer position in the remote station.
- Tap changer position in the Control Centre.
- Transformer Voltage.

D: Single line diagram of a 220/33 kV transformer.

E: Single line diagram of a tap changer.

F: Command button to control the tap changer.

G: Current date and time display.

Figure (4.1) Main Window

4.2 Starting of the Simulation

The first step in the program is to use the *Start Simulation* sub menu to start the simulation, when this menu is clicked the centre and remote station start communication with each other ,at first the centre sends request frame to the remote station ,after the remote station receives this frame and checks it, it sends a respond frame to the centre, during this negotiation the simulator displays a message informing the user to wait until the communication is established, when the negotiation finished the simulator displays a message showing that the communication is established, then the current step position of the transformer tap changer and the voltage shown in the station side and after a short delay in control centre side, this delay represents the signal transfer time from remote station to control centre. Those steps are shown in the figures (4.2), (4.3), (4.4), (4, 5) and (4.6).

Figure (4.2) Selection of the Start Simulation sub menu

Figure (4.3) Negotiation between centre and remote station

Figure (4.4) Communication with remote station OK

Figure (4.5) Current position of tap changer shown in the station side

Figure (4.6) Current Values of tap changer position and voltage
Shown in the control centre side

4.3 Tap changer Control

Depending on the voltage measurement and the tap changer position indication the user of the simulator can improve the voltage by controlling the tap changer position to guarantee the best voltage level and this can be done by sending commands to increment the tap position or to decrement it.

To increment the voltage level next steps are used:

The Tap Changer Control button is clicked; two buttons named Raise & Lower appeared.

The Raise button is clicked.

After a delay of about eight seconds the tap position incremented by one, this delay time is equal to the message transfer time in both directions plus the processing time of the command. Incrementing is shown in figures (4.7) and (4.8).

Figure (4.7) Main window after selecting the Control tap changer button

Figure (4.8) position indication incremented by one

To decrement the voltage level next steps are used:

The Tap Changer Control button is clicked; two buttons named Raise & Lower appeared.

The Lower button is clicked.

After the same delay time the tap position will decrement by one.

Figure (4.9) Position indication decremented by one

4.4 Simulator Alarms

The simulator is designed to alarm the user in two cases, when the voltage level is critical or when the tap changer reaches its higher or lower limits. In normal systems these alarms are generated in the remote station and then transferred to the centre, but in this simulation it has been generated at centre also.

4.4.1 Voltage Alarms

The voltage in the secondary side of the transformer is designed to be in the range between 29 and 36kV, if the voltage measurement is not in the required level an alarm message displays showing that the measurement is either Too High or Too Low.

This is shown in figures (4.10) and (4.11).

Figure (4.10) Voltage Too High Alarm Message

Figure (4.11) Voltage Too Low Alarm Message

4.4.2 Tap Position Alarms

The 220/33 kV transformer tap changer position is ranged from 1 to 21 to give the voltage range between 29 and 36 kV, when the tap is in the end position (High or Low) the simulator generates an alarm message showing that the tap is in the end position and in this case the corresponding command button is disabled to prevent the operator from sending wrong command.

Figure (4.12) Tap in Min Position Alarm

Figure (4.13) Lower Command Button Disabled

Figure (4.14) Tap in Max Position Alarm

Figure (4.15) Raise Command Button Disabled

4.5 Message Frames

In order to let the simulator user understands the protocol behavior four sub menus are added to the simulation program .

To see the centre request frame sent to the remote station next steps were used:

The Message Structure Menu is clicked.

The Centre request frame sub Menu is clicked

A form displayed showing the frame elements in binary and decimal format.

Figure (4.16) Selection of Message Structure Menu

Figure (4.17) Centre request frame

To see the station Respond frame sent to the centre next steps were used:

The Message Structure Menu is clicked.

The Station Respond sub Menu is clicked.

A form displayed showing the frame elements in binary and decimal format.

Figure (4.18) Station Respond frame

to see the last frame sent from the control centre to the remote station next steps were used :

The Message Structure Menu is clicked.

The Frames from Centre sub Menu is clicked.

A form displayed showing the last frame elements in binary and decimal format.

Figure (4.19) Form shows Frame from Centre

To see the last frame sent to the control centre from the remote station next steps were used:

The *Message Structure* Menu is clicked.

The *Frames from Remote Station* sub Menu is clicked.

A form displayed showing the last frame elements in binary and decimal format.

Figure (4.20) Form shows Frame from Station

Chapter 5

**Conclusions
&
Recommendations**

5.1 Conclusion

The use of SCADA systems in power networks is very helpful .It reduces the number of employees in utilities ,the cost of routine visits to remote facilities and it makes the control of power networks easier. The main use of SCADA system is to carry control signals (commands, measurements, status and alarms) between devices.

In this simulation, a control centre and a remote station were connected using IEC60870-5-101 protocol. Regulating commands were sent from the control centre to the remote station in order to raise or lower the tap changer position then the new Step position indications were transferred from the remote station to the control centre.

The simulation contained additional functions that didn't take part in the existing SCADA system in the power networks. [1], [4], [6]

- In the existing systems the alarms are usually generated in the remote station devices and sent to the centre, but in this simulation some alarms have been generated in the centre depending on the measurement' s values and position indications (it generates the alarm in a certain threshold value)
- The second function added is the operation interlocks; depending on the state of station devices the software in centre prevents the user from operating field devices to avoid mal operations.

5.2 Recommendation

This research covered most of the theoretical aspects of the SCADA system. Depending on the message structure of the IEC60870-5-101 protocol, the simulation program is implemented and covered small part of the protocol functions, such as initiation procedure, sending regulating commands and receiving step position indications.

The program was constructed in such a way that it is possible to implement new types of signals (measured values or alarms) , because the protocol supports different types of signals. Function bits in the control field, type identification and cause of transmission can be altered to represent different signals.

For future work, the simulation program needs future development to include all the remaining protocol functions that cover all types of messages such as

- Measurement (voltage, current, active power, reactive power, power factor, frequency...etc).
- Status signals (on, off, local, remote ...etc).
- Alarms.
- Switching commands (open and close).

References

1. RF-Rogaland Research, “Norwegian IEC 870-5-101, User Conventions”, version 2.0, 2000.
2. ABB Utilities GmbH., “Host communication Interface with IEC 60870-5-104”, 2002.
3. G. Barry Cole, “GBC REPORTS ABOUT IEC 60870-5-101”, 2002/2003.
4. Siemens-NEC Sudan, IEC 60870-5-104 Interoperability, version1.1, 2004.
5. International Electro technical Commission Web site, Pages at 870-5-101 © IEC, 1995.
6. Siemens-NEC Sudan, Tele-control -Interface Book, version 1.0.0.2, 2005.
7. William Stalling, “Data & Computer Communications”, 4th Edition

Appendices

Appendix A: Program Source

{Function to convert from decimal to binary}

Public Enum Bases

 ebBinary = 2&

 ebDecimal = 10&

End Enum

Private Function Floor(ByVal Number As Double) As Double

 If Int(Number) > Number Then

 Floor = Int(Number) - 1

 Else

 Floor = Int(Number)

 End If

End Function

Private Function ConvertDigit(IngDigit As Long, BASE As Bases) As String

 If IngDigit >= BASE Then

 Err.Raise ERROR_NUMBER, "ConvertDigit", "Invalid digit for base"

 Else

 Select Case BASE

 Case ebBinary, ebDecimal:

 ConvertDigit = CStr(IngDigit)

 End Select

 End If

End Function

Private Function ConvertDec2Base(ByVal Number, ByVal BASE As Bases, Optional NumDecimals As Long = -1, Optional Tolerance As Double = 1E-27, Optional PadTo As Long = 0) As String

 Dim dblTemp As Double

 Dim ICDec As Long

 Dim IDigit As Long

 Dim dblPwr As Double

 Dim strTemp As String

 If Not IsNumeric(Number) Then

 Err.Raise ERROR_NUMBER, "ConvertDec2Base", "Number must be decimal"

 ElseIf BASE < 2 Then

 Err.Raise ERROR_NUMBER, "ConvertDec2Base", "Invalid base"

 Else

 'Negative tolerance could cause loops

 Tolerance = Abs(Tolerance)

 dblTemp = CDbl(Number)

 If dblTemp < 0 Then

 strTemp = "-"

 dblTemp = -dblTemp

 End If

 ICDec = 8

 If ICDec = 0 Then

 strTemp = strTemp & "0"

```

Else
  Do Until ICDec = 0
    ICDec = ICDec - 1
    dblPwr = BASE ^ ICDec
    IDigit = 0
    Do While dblTemp >= dblPwr
      IDigit = IDigit + 1
      dblTemp = dblTemp - dblPwr
    Loop
    strTemp = strTemp & ConvertDigit(IDigit, BASE)
  Loop
End If
  ConvertDec2Base = strTemp
End If

```

End Function

{End of the function Decimal to Binary}

"Start the Simulation"

```

Private Sub start_Click()
  Command1.Enabled = True
  Command2.Enabled = True
  Command3.Enabled = True

```

{Centre Constructs the request status frame}

```

Form5.Startcharacter.Text = 16
Form5.ControlFiled.Text = 73
Form5.CheckSum = 0
Form5.StopCharacter = 22

```

"conversion of frame to binary"

```

Form5.StartcharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form5.Startcharacter.Text), ebBinary)
Form5.ControlFiledBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form5.ControlFiled.Text), ebBinary)
Form5.CheckSumBin = "00000000"
Form5.StopCharacterBin = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form5.StopCharacter), ebBinary)

```

{Station checks the request status frame}

```

If Form5.Startcharacter.Text = 16 Then
  If Form5.ControlFiled.Text = 73 Then
    If Form5.CheckSum = 0 Then
      If Form5.StopCharacter = 22 Then
        Form4.Show
      Form4.Label1.Caption = " Stablising Communication with Remote Station"
      delayTime = 0.00003
      tempTime = Time
      Do Until Time > tempTime + delayTime
        DoEvents
      Loop
      Form4.Hide
    End If
  End If
End If

```

End If
End If
End If
End If

{Station Construct the Respond frame}

Form6.Startcharacter.Text = 16
Form6.ControlFiled.Text = 11
Form6.CheckSum = 0
Form6.StopCharacter = 22

"Convert frame to binary"

Form6.StartcharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form6.Startcharacter.Text), ebBinary)
Form6.ControlFiledBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form6.ControlFiled.Text), ebBinary)
Form6.CheckSumBin = "00000000"
Form6.StopCharacterBin = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form6.StopCharacter), ebBinary)

{Centre checks the Respond frame}

If Form6.Startcharacter.Text = 16 Then
If Form6.ControlFiled.Text = 11 Then
If Form6.CheckSum = 0 Then
If Form6.StopCharacter = 22 Then
Form4.Show
Form4.Label1.Caption = " Remote Station connected "
delayTime = 0.000005
tempTime = Time
Do Until Time > tempTime + delayTime
DoEvents
Loop
Form4.Hide
End If
End If
End If
End If

"Station generates starting value of the tap position"

Text1.Text = Int(6 * Rnd) + 8

{Station Construct the data frame to centre}

Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68
Form3.txtFramelength1.Text = 6
Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6
Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68
Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8
Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5
Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1
Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 2
Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10

```

Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30
Form3.txtInformationElement.Text = Val(Text1.Text)
Form3.txtChecksum.Text = Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text) + Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text) +
Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text)
Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68

```

"convert the frame to binary"

```

Form3.txtStartcharacter1Bin.Text =
ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtFramelength1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFramelength1.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtFramelength2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtStartcharacter2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtControlFieldBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtControlField.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtTypeIdentificationBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifierBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtCauseofTransmissionBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtCommonAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtInformationObjectAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtInformationElementBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtChecksumBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtChecksum), ebBinary)
Form3.txtStopCharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text), ebBinary)

```

{Centre checks the received data frame from station}

```

If Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68 Then
If Form3.txtFramelength1.Text = 6 Then
If Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6 Then
If Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68 Then
If Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8 Then
If Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5 Then
If Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1 Then
If Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 2 Then
If Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10 Then
If Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30 Then
If Form3.txtInformationElement.Text = Val(Text1.Text) Then
If Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68 Then
delayTime = 0.00001
tempTime = Time
Do Until Time > tempTime + delayTime
DoEvents
Loop
Text2.Text = Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text)
Text3.Text = (6 * Rnd) + 29
End If
End If
End If
End If
End If

```

```
End If
```

"clearing the ip/op buffers"

```
Form2.txtStartcharacter1 = clr
Form2.txtFramelength1 = clr
Form2.txtFrameLength2 = clr
Form2.txtStartcharacter2 = clr
Form2.txtControlField = clr
Form2.txtTypeIdentification = clr
Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier = clr
Form2.txtCauseofTransmission = clr
Form2.txtCommonAddress = clr
Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress = clr
Form2.txtStopCharacter = clr
Form2.txtInformationElement = clr
End Sub
```

"raise command"

```
Private Sub Command2_Click()
Command2.Enabled = False
```

{Centre Construct the data frame to station}

```
Form2.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68
Form2.txtFramelength1.Text = 6
Form2.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6
Form2.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68
Form2.txtControlField.Text = 65
Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 47
Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1
Form2.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 6
Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10
Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 40
Form2.txtInformationElement.Text = 2
Form2.txtChecksum.Text = Val(Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text) + Val(Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text) +
Val(Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text) + Val(Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text) + Val(Form2.txtInformationElement.Text)
Form2.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68
```

"convert frame to binary"

```
Form2.txtStartcharacter1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtStartcharacter1.Text), ebBinary)
Form2.txtFramelength1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtFramelength1.Text), ebBinary)
Form2.txtFramelength2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtFrameLength2.Text), ebBinary)
Form2.txtStartcharacter2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtStartcharacter2.Text), ebBinary)
```



```

Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8
Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5
Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1
Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 11
Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10
Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30
Form3.txtInformationElement.Text = Val(Text1.Text)
Form3.txtChecksum.Text = Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text) + Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text) +
Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text)
Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68

```

"convert frame to binary"

```

Form3.txtStartcharacter1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtFramelength1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFramelength1.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtFramelength2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtStartcharacter2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtControlFieldBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtControlField.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtTypeIdentificationBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifierBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtCauseofTransmissionBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtCommonAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtInformationObjectAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtInformationElementBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text), ebBinary)
Form3.txtChecksumBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtChecksum), ebBinary)
Form3.txtStopCharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text), ebBinary)

```

{Centre checks the received frame from station}

```

If Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6 Then
If Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68 Then
If Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8 Then
If Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5 Then
If Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1 Then
If Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 11 Then
If Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10 Then
If Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30 Then
If Form3.txtInformationElement.Text = Val(Text2.Text + 1) Then
If Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68 Then
    delayTime = 0.00001
    tempTime = Time
    Do Until Time > tempTime + delayTime
    DoEvents
    Loop
    Text2.Text = Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text)
    Text3.Text = Text3.Text + 0.4
    If Text3.Text > 36 Then
    MsgBox "          VOLTAGE IS TOO HIGH !!!          ", vbOKOnly + vbCritical
    End If

```

```

    End If
    Command2.Enabled = True
    If Text1.Text = 20 Then
Label6.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else
Label6.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 21 Then
Label5.ForeColor = &HFF&
    MsgBox "          MAXIMUM TAP POSITION REACHED !!!          ", vbOKOnly + vbExclamation
    Command2.Enabled = False
    Else
Label5.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 19 Then
Label7.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else
Label7.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 18 Then
Label8.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else
Label8.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 17 Then
Label9.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else
Label9.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 16 Then
Label22.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else
Label22.ForeColor = &H80000007
    End If
    If Text1.Text = 15 Then
Label21.ForeColor = &HFF&
    Else

```

```
Label21.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 14 Then
Label20.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label20.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 13 Then
Label19.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label19.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 12 Then
Label18.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label18.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 11 Then
Label17.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label17.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 10 Then
Label16.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label16.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 9 Then
Label15.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label15.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 8 Then
Label13.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label13.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 7 Then
Label12.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label12.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 6 Then
Label14.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label14.ForeColor = &H80000007
```

```

End If
If Text1.Text = 5 Then
Label11.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label11.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 4 Then
Label10.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label10.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 3 Then
Label23.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label23.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 2 Then
Command3.Enabled = True
Label24.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label24.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 1 Then
Label25.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label25.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
End Sub

```

"Lower command"

```

Private Sub Command3_Click()
Command3.Enabled = False

```

{Centre construct the data frame to station}

```

Form2.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68
Form2.txtFramelength1.Text = 6
Form2.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6
Form2.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68
Form2.txtControlField.Text = 65
Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 47
Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1
Form2.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 6
Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10
Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 40
Form2.txtInformationElement.Text = 1
Form3.txtChecksum.Text = Val(Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text) + Val(Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text) +
Val(Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text) + Val(Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text) + Val(Form2.txtInformationElement.Text)

```

Form2.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68

"convert frame to binary"

Form2.txtStartcharacter1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtStartcharacter1.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtFramelength1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtFramelength1.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtFramelength2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtFrameLength2.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtStartcharacter2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtStartcharacter2.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtControlFieldBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtControlField.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtTypeIdentificationBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifierBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtCauseofTransmissionBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtCauseofTransmission.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtCommonAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtInformationObjectAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtInformationElementBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtInformationElement.Text), ebBinary)

Form2.txtChecksumBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtChecksum), ebBinary)

Form2.txtStopCharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form2.txtStopCharacter.Text), ebBinary)

{Station checks the received data frame from centre}

If Form2.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68 Then

If Form2.txtFramelength1.Text = 6 Then

If Form2.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6 Then

If Form2.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68 Then

If Form2.txtControlField.Text = 65 Then

If Form2.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 47 Then

If Form2.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1 Then

If Form2.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 6 Then

If Form2.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10 Then

If Form2.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 40 Then

If Form2.txtInformationElement.Text = 1 Then

If Form2.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68 Then

delayTime = 0.00005

tempTime = Time

Do Until Time > tempTime + delayTime

DoEvents

Loop

Text1.Text = Text1.Text - 1

End If

{Station constructs the data frame to centre}

Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68

Form3.txtFramelength1.Text = 6

Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6

Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68

Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8

Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5

Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1

Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 11

Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10

Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30

Form3.txtInformationElement = Val(Text1.Text)

Form3.txtChecksum.Text = Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text) + Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text) +
Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text) + Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text)

Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68

"convert frame to binary"

Form3.txtStartcharacter1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtFramelength1Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFramelength1.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtFramelength2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtStartcharacter2Bin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtControlFieldBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtControlField.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtTypeIdentificationBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifierBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtCauseofTransmissionBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtCommonAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtInformationObjectAddressBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtInformationElementBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtInformationElement.Text), ebBinary)

Form3.txtChecksumBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtChecksum), ebBinary)

Form3.txtStopCharacterBin.Text = ConvertDec2Base(Val(Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text), ebBinary)

{Centre checks the received frame from station}

If Form3.txtStartcharacter1.Text = 68 Then

If Form3.txtFramelength1.Text = 6 Then

If Form3.txtFrameLength2.Text = 6 Then

If Form3.txtStartcharacter2.Text = 68 Then

If Form3.txtControlField.Text = 8 Then

If Form3.txtTypeIdentification.Text = 5 Then

If Form3.txtVariableStructureQualifier.Text = 1 Then

If Form3.txtCauseofTransmission.Text = 11 Then

If Form3.txtCommonAddress.Text = 10 Then

If Form3.txtInformationObjectAddress.Text = 30 Then

If Form3.txtInformationElement = Val(Text2.Text - 1) Then

If Form3.txtStopCharacter.Text = 68 Then

delayTime = 0.00001


```
Label9.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 16 Then
Label22.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label22.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 15 Then
Label21.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label21.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 14 Then
Label20.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label20.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 13 Then
Label19.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label19.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 12 Then
Label18.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label18.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 11 Then
Label17.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label17.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 10 Then
Label16.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label16.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 9 Then
Label15.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label15.ForeColor = &H8000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 8 Then
Label13.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label13.ForeColor = &H8000007
```

```

End If
If Text1.Text = 7 Then
Label12.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label12.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 6 Then
Label14.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label14.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 5 Then
Label11.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label11.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 4 Then
Label10.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label10.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 3 Then
Label23.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label23.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 2 Then
Label24.ForeColor = &HFF&
Else
Label24.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
If Text1.Text = 1 Then
Label25.ForeColor = &HFF&
MsgBox "          MIN TAP POSITION REACHED   !!!          ", vbOKOnly + vbCritical
Command3.Enabled = False
Else
Label25.ForeColor = &H80000007
End If
End Sub
Private Sub Image1_Click()
Image1.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image2.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image3.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image4.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image5.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image6.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)

```

```
Image7.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image8.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image9.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image10.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image11.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image12.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image13.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image14.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image15.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image16.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image17.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image18.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image19.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image20.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
Image21.Picture = LoadResPicture(101, 0)
End Sub
```

"Tap changer control selection "

```
Private Sub Command1_Click()
Command1.Visible = False
Frame2.Visible = True
Command2.Visible = True
Command3.Visible = True
End Sub
```

"Show the Respond frame"

```
Private Sub ack_Click()
Form6.Show
End Sub
```

"Show the date and time"

```
Private Sub Timer1_Timer()
Label4.Caption = Now
End Sub
```

"Show the centre data frame"

```
Private Sub Centre_Click()
Form2.Show
End Sub
```

"Show the station data frame"

```
Private Sub Station_Click()
Form3.Show
End Sub
```

"Show the request frame"

```
Private Sub request_Click()
Form5.Show
```

End Sub

"End the simulation"

Private Sub quit_Click()

End

End Sub

Appendix B: Possibilities of cause of transmission

<0>:= not used
<1>:= periodic, cyclic
<2>:= background scan
<3>:= spontaneous
<4>:= initialized
<5>:= request or requested
<6>:= activation
<7>:= activation confirmation
<8>:= deactivation
<9>:= deactivation confirmation
<10>:= activation termination
<11>:= return information caused by a remote command
<12>:= return information caused by a local command
<13>:= file transfer
<14..19>:= reserved for further compatible definitions
<20>:= interrogated by general interrogation
<21>:= interrogated by group 1 interrogation
<22>:= interrogated by group 2 interrogation
<23>:= interrogated by group 3 interrogation
<24>:= interrogated by group 4 interrogation
<25>:= interrogated by group 5 interrogation
<26>:= interrogated by group 6 interrogation
<27>:= interrogated by group 7 interrogation
<28>:= interrogated by group 8 interrogation
<29>:= interrogated by group 9 interrogation
<30>:= interrogated by group 10 interrogation
<31>:= interrogated by group 11 interrogation
<32>:= interrogated by group 12 interrogation
<33>:= interrogated by group 13 interrogation
<34>:= interrogated by group 14 interrogation
<35>:= interrogated by group 15 interrogation
<36>:= interrogated by group 16 interrogation
<37>:= requested by general counter request
<38>:= requested by group 1 counter request
<39>:= requested by group 2 counter request
<40>:= requested by group 3 counter request
<41>:= requested by group 4 counter request
<42..47>:= reserved for further compatible definitions

Appendix C: Control field bits

RES	Reserved
PRM	Primary message 0 = message from secondary (responding) station 1 = message from primary (initiating) station.
FCB	Frame count bit. 0-1 = alternating bit for successive send/confirm or request/respond service per station The frame count bit is used to delete losses and duplications of information transfers.
FCV	Frame count valid 0 = alternating function FCB bit is invalid. 1 = alternating function of FCB bit is valid. Some messages and services that ignore the deletion of duplication or less of information output do not alternate the FCB bit and indicates this by a cleared FCV bit.
DFC	Data flow control 0 = further message are acceptable. 1 = further message may cause data overflow.
ACD	Access demand 0 = no access demand for class 1 data transmission (used for events or for high priority messages). 1 = access demand for class 1 data transmission.

Appendix D: General structure of the ASDU message

